

CURRENT ISSUES IN IMPLEMENTING COMPLIANCE CONTROL IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

Ulashvayev Shohruh Abdivaxobovich

Researcher of Tashkent State Institute of Economics

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Abstract. The scientific article examines the basic concepts of compliance control as an important tool of financial monitoring in order to combat money laundering in commercial banks. The main directions for the development of compliance control in banks are also proposed.

Key words: compliance control, financial monitoring, bank, prevention of money laundering, terrorist financing, Basel.

Currently, during the global financial globalization, financial management is significantly intensifying, in particular, under the influence of growing demands to improve the effectiveness of financial monitoring, as an essential part of financial control in order to combat money laundering.

The issue of combating corruption by introducing a compliance control system in the banking sector has become relevant for the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Justice, the Prosecutor General's Office, the UNDP anti-corruption project, KPMG. It was attended by employees of the Central Bank, managers and specialists of commercial banks operating in the compliance control system. Measures are being taken to introduce a compliance control system, foreign experience and international standards in the process of introducing this system into the banking sector. The goal is to increase legal literacy and legal knowledge of employees of the Central Bank and commercial banks in the direction of compliance control.[6]

The basic factors for the growth of the role of financial monitoring of second-tier banks in managing risks associated with money laundering are:

- increasing threats to financial security, especially in modern conditions of expansion of shadow, illegal activities;
- the growth of high-tech financial innovations that have unique capabilities for realizing various types of interests of business entities;
- large-scale liberalization of capital movements;
- accessibility of the global financial market, in particular offshore zones for money laundering for unscrupulous business entities [1].

An important tool for the development of financial monitoring is compliance control in the security system in commercial banks. Let's consider the basic concepts of compliance control in second-tier banks.

Compliance (eng. compliance - agreement, conformity; comes from the verb to comply - to comply) - means action in accordance with a request or instruction; obedience [2].

“Compliance” is compliance with any internal or external requirements or regulations. Compliance refers to the part of the management / control system in an organization associated with the risks of non-compliance, non-compliance with legal requirements, regulations, rules and standards of supervisory authorities, industry associations and self-regulatory organizations, codes of conduct, etc. Such non-compliance risks may ultimately manifest in the form of legal or regulatory sanctions, financial or reputational losses as a result of non-compliance with laws, generally accepted rules and standards [3].

Bank regulatory compliance is a general term for banks designing their policies and practices to align with any rules they are required to follow. This includes any applicable local government or international laws, as well as any local or international rules from financial regulatory agencies.

Compliance control as a corporate ideology acts as a means of propaganda aimed at promoting requirements for compliance with the internal standards of the enterprise and generally accepted social values. The implementation of such a compliance ideology involves the creation of conditions so that company representatives, when performing certain actions, are guided by the standards that compliance control presupposes. If in our country the corporate ideology of compliance is in its infancy, then in most developed countries various areas of compliance control have become firmly established in all sectors of business and economic activity.[6]

Fig.1. MetricStream Compliance Risk Management Lifecycle [8]

Compliance with laws, regulations and compliance standards generally concerns issues such as maintaining appropriate standards of market conduct, managing conflicts of interest, treating clients fairly and ensuring integrity in advising clients. The scope of compliance also includes specific areas, such as: combating money laundering and the financing of terrorism; development of documents and procedures to ensure compliance of the company's activities with current legislation; protecting information flows, combating fraud and corruption, establishing ethical standards of employee behavior, etc. [4].

Document of the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision "Compliance and its functions in banks" in 2005, which considered the following main points, such as the special status of the compliance control service in banks is noted; compliance risk management should be in each bank in accordance with the specifics of the bank's activities [5].

Measures to combat money laundering and terrorist financing help the bank solve several problems at once. In particular, collecting information on a systematic basis during identification and verification

clients, which allows you to: create a database for future risk forecasts, identify transactions subject to mandatory control and identify suspicious transactions; document these above measures, highlighting the main directions for the development of the financial monitoring mechanism; storage of information and information obtained as a result of internal control to combat money laundering and terrorist financing; continuous improvement of compliance control and development of its tools; continuous training and advanced training of bank employees performing compliance control.

One of the main elements of managing compliance risks (mainly legal and the risk of loss of business reputation) of a credit organization is the "Know Your Customer" principle (hereinafter referred to as KYC). In order to comply with the KYC principle, it is recommended that a credit institution develop adequate policies and procedures, including the procedure for carrying out banking operations and other transactions, customer identification programs, identification and identification of beneficiaries, monitoring of cash flows through bank accounts and bank risk management.

It is recommended that a credit institution comply with the KYC principle in order to ensure compliance with the legislation of the country, including on

issues of combating the legalization (laundering) of proceeds from crime and the financing of terrorism, compliance of the credit institution's activities with business customs and principles of professional ethics, as well as ensuring stability of the financial position of the credit institution.

The KYC principle, like many other best banking practices, came to us from abroad. Reviewing the results of an internal study of transnational bank transfers in 1999, the Basel Committee revealed that the "know your customer - KYC" policy in credit institutions in a number of countries was insufficiently effective. Based on the committee's research, KYC policies in a large number of countries had significant shortcomings, and was not implemented at all in others. Even in countries with well-developed financial markets, the level of effectiveness of KYC has proven to be different. In this regard, the Basel Committee submitted an application to the Working Group on Cross-Border Banking to study current KYC procedures and develop recommended standards acceptable to banks in all countries. The result was published as a consultation document in January 2001.[7]

In the conditions of modern competition, the issue of quality and reliability of the bank providing its services on the market is very acute. Compliance control is an effective way to reduce risks in a bank, as well as an effective tool for attracting clients and investors. Compliance is an important tool of the corporate governance system, necessary for management makes management decisions, and therefore contributes to the achievement of set goals, both strategic and tactical.

Thus, the main directions for the development of compliance control as a financial monitoring mechanism to neutralize the risk of money laundering in commercial banks consists of a proven monitoring mechanism for anti-money laundering measures; analysis of information provided by the client during his identification and verification, necessarily including information on financial stability and business activity; when monitoring, also identify client transactions subject to mandatory control and save this information and information obtained as a result of this control; as well as constantly improve the qualifications of bank employees.

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